

Resin Catalysed Hydrolysis of Propionamide

UMAKANT SENTIYA* and R. P. SHUKLA**

Department of Applied Chemistry, Government Engineering College, Jabalpur (M. P.)

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Kinetics of the reaction between amberlite IR-120 resin and propionamide solution have been studied at different temperatures as well as at different concentrations of the reactants. The reaction has been found to be pseudo first order. The rate constant increases with an increase in resin concentration and attains an optimum value. Arrhenius parameters have been computed. The mechanism has been proposed on the basis of experimental results.

THE acid catalysed hydrolysis of amides¹⁻¹⁵ specially propionamide^{1,5,7,9} has been studied by a number of workers and shown to involve a unimolecular mechanism. Further these reactions exhibit rate maxima when amide is added to a mineral acid, the velocity of hydrolysis reaches a maximum and then falls off with increased acid concentration. Edward and Meacock² explained that when amide is fully protonated, a further increase in acid concentration merely decreases the water activity. Benrath¹⁶ came to the conclusion that the velocity was greatest when sufficient acid was added to convert all the amide into a cation. When the acid concentration is increased beyond this point the cation combines with the anion to form an undissociated salt which does not react with water and hence the velocity falls off. Taylor¹⁷ arrived at a somewhat similar conclusion, e.g., increased acid concentration caused the formation of an unhydrolyzable complex between the acid and the amide. If these were the true explanations, then the molality of the acid at maximum velocity should vary with the concentration of the amide but this does not appear to be the case.

The mechanism of reaction suggested by Kriehle and Holst¹ involves the reaction of amide and acid as the primary step while Edward and Meacock² had shown amide and H⁺ ion as the primary step.

In view of various suggestions and even contradictory views of various workers^{2,16,17} it was thought proper to look for a mechanism which could explain rate maxima for this reaction. The kinetics of other reactions which are catalysed by resins have been studied by Nieto¹⁹ and others^{20,21,22}.

Experimental

The reaction was carried out in a vessel in which the resin Amberlite IR-120 (The Rohm and Haas Company, Philadelphia, U.S.A.) and the Propiona-

amide (Fluka A. G. Chemische Fabrik CH-9470 Buchs SG) solution were stirred continuously at constant rate using mercury seal glass stirrer. Kinetic measurements were carried out at the temperature chosen maintained within ± 0.5 by withdrawing aliquots at proper time intervals. The reaction rate was followed conductometrically⁴. Resistance at zero time was obtained by extrapolation and that at infinite time was noted at equilibrium (i.e., when no change in resistance was observed after sufficient time). The rate constant was calculated using the formula²³

$$k_1 = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{R_t (R_\infty - R_0)}{R_0 (R_\infty - R_t)}$$

where 'R_t', the resistance at time 't',

'R₀', the resistance at zero time,

'R_∞', the equilibrium resistance.

Total order was determined by using fractional life period method²³. Entropy of activation has been calculated by using the equation²³

$$K_r = \frac{kT}{h} e^{\Delta S/R} e^{-E/RT}$$

The results are recorded in tables given below :

TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARYING TEMPERATURES ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF PROPIONAMIDE

Propionamide (M)	Weight of Resin (gm)	Temperature (°C)	k ₁ × 10 ⁻³ (min ⁻¹)
1.0	10.0	35	0.9141
1.0	10.0	45	1.117
1.0	10.0	55	1.297

* Address for correspondence : Dr. U. K. Sentiya, 557, North Civil Lines, Beoharbag, Jabalpur, M.P.

** Dr. R. P. Shukla, Head of the Chemistry Department, Government Engineering College, Rewa, M.P.

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